

Comparative Evaluation of the Cytological Alteration in Buccal Mucosa and Oxidative Stress in Saliva of Children who are Smart Phone Users Versus Non Users - An Invivo Study

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Abstract

Background: In today's digital age, screens have become an integral part of children's lives, offering entertainment, education, and communication. While the benefits of technology are undeniable, excessive screen time can have adverse effects on various aspects of a child's health, including their oral health.

Aim: To evaluate and compare the cytological alteration in buccal mucosa and oxidative stress in saliva of children who are smart phone users versus non users.

Materials and Methodology: A questionnaire regarding the usage of smart phone was distributed among the parents of children. Among them, 40 children were selected on the basis of frequency of usage and were split into two equal groups: Group 1: no usage and Group 2: usage of 3-5 hours per day. The oxidative stress was evaluated in both the groups by measuring the level of enzyme catalase in the saliva. For the cytological evaluation buccal swab was obtained by using the conventional ice-cream stick method and the samples were subjected to histological and microscopical analysis to observe cytological alterations. The values were tabulated for statistical analysis.

Results: The results obtained showed a clinically significant difference between children who are smart phone users and non-users in terms of decreased catalase level causing oxidative stress and a higher frequency of cellular and chromosomal aberrations.

Conclusion: Hence it is concluded that there is a considerable effect of extended screen time on the oral health.

Keywords: Apoptotic cells, buccal mucosal cells, oxidative stress, catalase enzyme, radio-frequency electromagnetic radiation

Introduction

In the last decade, smartphones have revolutionized the way we communicate, work, and entertain ourselves, earning this era the title of the "decade of the smartphone." [1] The omnipresence of mobile devices has drastically altered human behavior, making screen time an integral part of daily life. Studies suggest that the average person touches their mobile phone an astonishing 2,617 times per day, and over a year, an individual spends approximately 800 hours engrossed in their device. This trend is even more pronounced among children, who are now referred to as digital natives due to their immersion in an ever-evolving digital ecosystem from an early age. Screen media has seamlessly woven itself into the fabric of childhood, offering unparalleled access to entertainment, education, and social interaction. While digital technology has numerous benefits such as providing learning resources, fostering creativity, and enabling instant communication the overuse of screens presents

significant concerns, particularly regarding children's physical and mental well-being. A survey conducted by Happinetz revealed that 42% of children under the age of 12 spend up to four hours daily glued to screens, raising alarms about the potential health risks associated with excessive screen exposure. One of the lesser discussed yet crucial aspects of prolonged screen exposure is its impact on children's oral health. Extended screen time often correlates with poor dietary habits, increased consumption of sugary snacks, and neglect of essential oral hygiene practices, leading to conditions such as cavities and gum disease. Furthermore, sedentary screen habits can contribute to obesity, which is linked to a higher risk of oral health problems. Beyond lifestyle concerns, the technology behind smart phones raises additional health related issues.

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The principle of smartphone functionality relies on radio-frequency electromagnetic waves (RF-EMW), particularly within the microwave frequency range of 300 MHz to 300 GHz². The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classified radiofrequency radiation as a possible carcinogen for humans in 2011³. Given these potential risks, the World Health Organization (WHO) has identified the effects of electromagnetic radiation (EMR) as a high-priority research area in its Research Agenda. In a recent research of 113 people aged 19 to 84 with phone usage ranging from 0 to 15 hours, DNA damage was discovered in buccal cells in patients who had been exposed to cell phone radiation for an extended period of time⁴. The scientists found that mobile phone users may have a higher risk of cancer and cytotoxicity. Research indicates that the effects of mobile phone use are proportional to the amount of time spent using it. Symptoms reported include burning sensations, tingling skin on the head and extremities, fatigue, sleeping disorders, vertigo, mental distraction, increased reaction time, diminished memory, headaches, weakness, palpitations, and digestive system disturbances⁵. This histological study aims to gain a better understanding of this relationship. With the increasing dependency on screens in modern life, it is imperative to understand and address the implications of prolonged exposure, particularly for children. This article explores the multifaceted impact of excessive screen time on children's health, focusing on its effects on oral health, dietary patterns, and potential radiation risks. As we navigate the digital age, it is essential to strike a balance between technological advancements and the well-being of future generations.⁶

Aim: The aim of the study was to assess the oxidative stress in saliva and cytological impact of extended screen time on buccal mucosa in children's oral health.

Objective

To compare and evaluate the level of enzyme catalase in saliva among screen time users and no screen time users.

To compare and evaluate the cytological alteration in the buccal mucosa of screen time users and no screen time users.

Materials Methodology

A basic questionnaire regarding the pattern and frequency of mobile usage by children was prepared and distributed among the parents visiting the department. The questionnaire was validated by two different examiners. The validated comprehensive questionnaire, along with a consent form, was then distributed to the parents/guardians.

Patient were categorized, based on the exposure to mobile phone electromagnetic radiation assessed through a questionnaire into two groups : Group 1: No usage, Group 2: Usage of 3-5 hours a day making the total sample 40 children in each group.

Inclusion criteria include (1) Children aged between 4 and 14 years are included, (2) Children with no systemic disorders, (3) Children not under any medication, (4) children who had been using smartphones for a minimum of 1 year.

Exclusion criteria were (1) Children with soft tissue lesions in the oral cavity (2) Children who are on long-term medication (3) Children with gingivitis (4) Children/parents who were not willing to be a part of the study

After allocating the child into a specific group based on a questionnaire clinical examination of oral cavity was performed to detect the presence of any soft tissue lesions. In the first visit The buccal mucosa samples were collected with prior consent from the parent. Swab was obtained by using a sterile ice-cream sticks from the inner walls of cheeks (buccal mucosa). Slide preparation was done. Slides were stained, air-dried, and observed under the microscope at 10 × and 40 × magnifications for cellular changes in buccal mucosa. In the Second visit, 5 ml of unstimulated fasting saliva was obtained and stored and transported to lab for catalase activity test. Collected data subjected to statistical analysis.

Screen time questionnaire

Consent form

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the ethical committee under the clearance number DJC/IEC/48/2024.

Normal Basal Cells

Evenly pigmented nucleus results in a higher nucleus-to-cytoplasm ratio. They are smaller in size and oval-shaped. There are no DNA-containing structures in these cells except for the nucleus.

Micronucleated Cells

Micronucleated cells are distinguished by the presence of a major nucleus and one or more tiny nuclear structures known as micronuclei. The micronuclei are round/oval in form, with diameters ranging from 1/3 to 1/16 of the major nucleus. The existence of these cells indicates chromosomal loss or fragmentation occurred during early nuclear division⁷.

Cells with Nuclear Buds

Nuclei with a strong constriction at one end indicate a budding process, which is the removal of nuclear material by budding. These were known as "broken egg" cells. The mechanism of nuclear bud (NB) production is not defined; however, it might be attributable to DNA repair⁸.

Condensed Chromatin

Condensed chromatin has a roughly striated appearance, whereas aggregated chromatin is heavily stained. In these cells, it is clear that chromatin is accumulating in certain sections of the nucleus while being lost in others. These cells may be in the early stages of apoptosis, however this has not been demonstrated definitively⁹.

Karyorrhetic Cells

Karyorrhetic cells exhibit larger nuclear chromatin aggregations than condensed chromatin cells (CC). They feature a

speckled nuclear pattern, indicating that the nucleus has fragmented and disintegrated. These cells may be in the late stage of apoptosis¹⁰.

Pyknotic cells

Pyknotic cells have a reduced nucleus that is evenly stained. The biological significance is that these cells may be experiencing a distinct type of cell death.

Karyolytic cells

Karyolytic cells have a decreased nucleus of DNA. These cells lack a nucleus and are at a late stage of cell death¹¹.

The observed cells in this study included Normal cells, Micro nucleated cells (MN), Pyknotic cells (PC), NB, Karyorrhetic cells (KR), Condensed Chromatin (CC), and Karyolytic cells (KL).

Oxidative Stress

Oxidative stress occurs when reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation increases uncontrollably and antioxidant defence proteins, such as superoxide dismutase and catalase, modify their function¹².

Results

The mucosal cells in the screen users were significantly higher in terms of Micro nucleated cells, Nuclear buds, Pyknotic cells, Karyorrhetic cells, Condensed Chromatin and Karyolytic Cells as compared to the non users with highly significant difference between the groups when analyzed using Independent t test

	Group I (Smartphone Non-User)	Group II (Smartphone Users)	T value	P value	Significance
Micro Nucleated Cells	0.679±0.231	4.674±1.475	11.9668	0.001*	Significant
Nuclear Bud	0.286±0.101	1.987±0.117	49.2166	0.001*	Significant
Pyknotic Cells	0.347±0.073	4.348±1.596	11.1995	0.001*	Significant
Karyorrhetic cells	6.798±1.485	23.856±8.284	21.2861	0.001*	Significant
Condensed Chromatin	10.757±3.686	34.734±9.532	26.6831	0.001*	Significant
Karyolytic Cells	4.697±1.596	24.183±7.454	25.5118	0.001*	Significant

MEAN FREQUENCIES OF BUCCAL MUCOSA CELLS IN SMARTPHONE USERS AND NON USERS

MEAN FREQUENCIES OF MICRO NUCLEATED, NUCLEAR BUDDING, PYKNOTIC CELLS, KARYORRHETIC CELLS, CONDENSED CHROMATIN AND KARYOLYTIC CELLS

usage of screen based devices when the comparison was done using the Independent t test

	Mean	Std Dev	Std Error	P value	Significance
Group I (Smartphone Non-Users)	259.47	11.484	1.458	0.001	Significant
Group II (Smartphone Users)	223.586	7.667	1.359		

INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF MEAN VALUES OF SMART PHONE USERS AND NON USERS

INTERGROUP COMPARISON OF MEAN VALUES OF SMART PHONE USERS AND NON USERS

Statistical Analysis

The data for the present study was entered in the Microsoft Excel 2007 and analyzed using the SPSS statistical software 23.0 Version. The descriptive statistics included mean, standard deviation standard error The level of the significance for the present study was fixed at 5%.

The intergroup comparison was done using the independent t tests based upon the normality of the data The Shapiro–Wilk test was used to investigate the distribution of the data and Levene's test to explore the homogeneity of the variables.

Discussion

The findings of this study emphasizes the potentially detrimental effects of prolonged screen time on children's oral health. Oxidative stress, as indicated by reduced catalase levels, can lead to cellular damage and contribute to oral health problems. The cytological changes in the buccal mucosa highlight

the direct impact of RF-EMW on oral tissues.

The American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) recognizes that children may be more vulnerable to the effects of radiofrequency electromagnetic radiation (RF-EMR) than adults.

Initially, researchers believed that low frequency electromagnetic fields (EMFs) would not affect human cells, as they do not increase tissue temperature or directly damage DNA. However, studies now show that radiofrequency (RF) radiation interacts with biological systems, leading to the increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can damage DNA. An individual's micronucleus (MN) count, a marker of genotoxicity, is influenced by environmental factors.¹³ An elevated MN count in exfoliated cells may indicate chromosomal alterations, defective mitosis, or chromosomal breakage. According to Tolbert et al. (1992), the MN index serves as a reliable, simple, and cost-effective tool for large-scale screenings.¹¹ Daroit NB et al. observed cytogenetic changes in the oral mucosa of individuals using mobile phones for more than 60 minutes per week over eight years, noting higher rates of nuclear abnormalities.⁵ Souza et al. (2014) found that mobile phone users who exceeded 5 hours of weekly usage had significantly more nuclear abnormalities.¹⁴

The NBUD is a biomarker for genotoxic events and chromosomal instability. PC cells have a shrunken nucleus, high nuclear material density, and strong stain. KR was discovered through nuclear chromatin aggregation, while cells with condensed chromatin, karyorrhectic, pyknotic, and KL are apoptotic. Detection of NBUD, PC, condensed cells, and KR in severely exposed samples indicates degeneration and early or late phases of apoptosis caused by RF-EMW effects. KL cells, which lack DNA and nuclei, represent a late stage of cell death. They are more prevalent among exposed people. The link between these indicators and health hazards has been effective in measuring cytotoxicity and genetic abnormalities.⁸ Even at low levels, RF-EMW can damage cell tissue and DNA, resulting in brain tumours, cancer, poor immunity, allergic reactions, inflammatory responses, headaches, anxiety, stress, chronic fatigue syndrome, and depression.⁵

Microscopically, in our study the above cells were detected considerably more in the heavily exposed samples, it can be assumed that these cells were degenerating and were in the early or late stages of apoptosis as a result of the RF-EMW impacts which is in accordance with Aravinda AS et al.⁵ In contrast to our study, Melt et al. reported that 850 MHz frequencies had no effect on DNA repair or synthesis.

Therefore, low radiation doses might not have immediate biological effects, they may still contribute to long-term damage through non-stochastic mechanisms.¹⁵

However, there is a noticeable research gap regarding the effects of RF-EMW on the oral cavity in children. Most available literature focuses on adults. Notably, Yadav AS and Sharma MK documented cytological changes in cells due to RF-EMW, findings that align with the current study.¹⁶

The body and saliva contain two types of antioxidants: enzymatic antioxidants like catalase and superoxide dismutase, and non-enzymatic antioxidants like diet supplements and small molecules like vitamin C, vitamin E, and uric acid.¹⁷ However, limited studies have evaluated saliva, and whole saliva is better for antioxidants due to its composition of gingival crevicular fluid, salivary gland secretions, and components from non-salivary origin in the oral cavity. Unstimulated whole saliva has a higher concentration of antioxidants than stimulated individual salivary

gland secretions.¹⁸ To the best of our knowledge, very limited investigations have been performed on salivary antioxidative changes in relation to radiofrequency electromagnetic waves. (RF-EW) have been studied for their effect on saliva catalase levels in children, marking the first study to evaluate these effects.

Excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) exposure, such as electromagnetic fields, can impair antioxidant defence systems, resulting in oxidative stress, in which free radical generation can overwhelm antioxidant defences, reducing their effectiveness¹⁹. EMFs in many species' systems can cause oxidative stress, as well as other biochemical and physiological changes.

Cellular alterations impact an organism's reactivity, with the balance of antioxidants and anti-oxidants governed by the formation and neutralisation of reactive oxygen species. Disrupting this equilibrium can cause diseases, such as free radical disorders, when reactive oxygen species react with cell components¹².

Canseven et al. studied the impact of a low frequency electromagnetic field (50 Hz and 1, 2, and 3 mT) on free radicals, antioxidants, and respiratory burst system activity in guinea pigs' hearts and livers. The study found that the intensity and duration of exposure affect the formation of free radicals and antioxidant enzyme activity.²⁰

Chu et al. found that EMF at 60 Hz frequency and 2.3 mT induction increased ROS while decreasing SOD activity in rat cerebellar cells after 3 hours of exposure²¹. Research shows that electromagnetic radiation affects superoxide dismutase activity, with cellular phone radiation reducing activity in erythrocytes and blood platelets²².

Catalase, an enzyme that converts excess hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen, was found to increase after exposure to electromagnetic radiation for 30 or 60 minutes at a field intensity of 150 V/m. However, after 30 minutes of exposure to EMF at 220 V/m, catalase activity declined dramatically after 60 minutes. This suggests that exposure to electromagnetic radiation may cause an increase in reactive oxygen species (ROS), which could be compensated for by increased catalase activity. Higher intensity and longer exposure time reduced antioxidant defense capacity, resulting in a decrease in catalase activity²³.

Electromagnetic field exposure led to a decrease in enzyme activity and lower CAT levels in rats, as well as oxidative stress in developing embryos, which persisted until day 21 following delivery, according to a study by Odaci et al.²⁴. According to Vuokko et al., electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure raised the production of free radicals and lipid peroxidation while depressing antioxidant systems and Mobile phones caused oxidative damage to cells by increasing the activity of carbonyl groups and xanthine oxidase while decreasing CAT activity.²⁵

The enzyme catalase is indirectly proportional to oxidative stress therefore the decrease in catalase level lead to cellular damage because of increased release of free radicals contributing to oral health problems which is in accordance with the Lewicka M et al.¹² and Buczko P et al.²⁶

This study is one of its kind as there is no past literature supporting the association of oxidative stress and cytological alteration of buccal mucosa with increased smart phone usage in children. Therefore, the findings from this study highlight the potential negative impact of extended screen time on children's oral health. The decrease in catalase levels and increased cytological alterations in screen time users indicate a need for further research and awareness regarding the consequences of

excessive screen time on oral health. Implementing strategies to mitigate the effects of prolonged screen exposure on oral tissues is crucial in promoting overall oral health in children.

Conclusion

The increased cytological alterations and decrease in catalase levels in smart phone users indicate a need for further research and awareness regarding the consequences of excessive screen time on oral health. Implementing strategies to mitigate the effects of prolonged screen exposure on oral tissues is crucial in promoting overall oral health in children.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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